

ISic0014

I.Sicily inscription 0014

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Iuliae · Au[g](ustae)
2. matri · castro[r](um)
3. Imp(eratoris) · L(uci) · Septimi · Severi · P[ri]m[us]
4. P[er]tina[ci]s A[ug]ust[us] · Arabi[ci]s
5. [AdiabeniParthi]m[aximi]m[ag]n[us]
6. [---]

Apparatus

Text of ILMusPalermo

Translation (en)

To Julia Augusta, Mother of the Camp, (wife) of Emperor Lucius Septimius Severus Pius Pertinax Augustus, victor in Arabia and Adiabene, great victor in Parthia [...]

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175727
EDR 074901
EDCS 9701489

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1968.0200

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 14

Raepsaet-Charlier, M.-Th. 1974. A propos du récent catalogue d'inscriptions latines du musée de Palerme. *Latomus*. 33: 124-127. At 125

Bivona, L 1967. Una nuova dedica a Giulia Domna. *Kokalos*. 13: 205-215.

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0014. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4333771>